

Advanced Manufacturing of Biobased products for urban outdoor applications through iNnovative CharactErisation, digital technologies, and circular approach.

Deliverable

D5.5 Initial Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR)

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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	2
List of Figures	3
List of Tables	4
List of Acronyms	5
Disclaimer	6
Scope	7
Abstract	8
1 Plan for Communication and Dissemination	9
1.1 Key messages	9
1.2 Target audience	10
1.3 Timeline.....	11
2 Communication strategy	13
2.1 Introduction	13
2.2 Objectives	13
2.3 Communication Matrix.....	13
3 Communication Activities and Channels	14
3.1 Visual Identity	14
3.1.1 Logotype Design.....	15
3.1.2 Logo Styles.....	15
3.1.3 AMBIANCE Colour Scheme	16
3.1.4 Typography.....	16
3.1.5 Design Elements and Illustrations	17
3.2 Communication Materials	18
3.2.1 Leaflet.....	18
3.2.2 Poster and Banner	21
3.3 Templates	22
3.3.1 Deliverable	22
3.3.2 Agenda.....	23
3.3.3 Minutes of Meeting	24
3.3.4 Presentation	25
3.4 Website	29
3.4.1 Website Structure	29
3.4.2 Essential Technical Features	30
3.4.3 Aesthetic Elements	30
3.4.4 Main Pages	30
3.5 Social Media	37
3.5.1 Twitter	38
3.5.2 LinkedIn	39
3.5.3 Other Accounts	39
3.6 Press Releases.....	40

3.7	Newsletters	40
3.8	Internal Communication Campaign.....	41
3.8.1	Social Media Plan.....	41
3.8.2	Reporting Forms	42
4	Dissemination strategy.....	43
4.1	Introduction	43
4.2	AMBIANCE dissemination strategy	43
4.3	Dissemination Channels	44
4.4	Clustering activities	45
4.5	Scientific Articles	46
4.6	Networking with European Associations	46
4.6.1	Biopolymers associations	46
5	Exploitation – General Overview	47
5.1	Exploitation in AMBIANCE – Objectives and strategy.....	47
6	Exploitation-Identify phase	50
6.1	Characterization of the AMBIANCE Exploitable results	50
1	IPR strategy	54
7	Conclusion	56
	Annex I. Exploitable Results Characterization Survey.....	57
7.1	KER#2A Advanced manufacturing processes: Artificial Turf.....	57

List of Figures

Figure 1: AIDA Model	12
Figure 2: Logo Option 1	14
Figure 3: Logo Option 2	14
Figure 4: Logo Poll Results.....	15
Figure 5: Logo Design Elements	15
Figure 6: AMBIANCE Logo Styles	16
Figure 7: Project’s Colour Palette	16
Figure 8: Communication Materials Font	17
Figure 9: Website Font	17
Figure 10: Icons in dark background.....	17
Figure 11: Visualisation of the project’s concept	18
Figure 12: Leaflet Front Cover 1/5.....	19
Figure 13: Leaflet – Project & Impact 2/5.....	19
Figure 14: Leaflet – Use Cases 3/5.....	20
Figure 15: Leaflet – Consortium 4/5	20
Figure 16: Leaflet – Back Cover 5/5	21
Figure 17: Poster.....	22
Figure 18: Banner	22
Figure 19: Deliverables Template	23
Figure 20: Agenda Template	24
Figure 21: Minutes of Meeting Template (MoM)	25
Figure 22: Presentation’s Title Slide with Light Background	26

Figure 23: Presentation’s Title Slide with Dark Background.....	26
Figure 24: Work Package Description Slide	27
Figure 25: Transitional Slide	27
Figure 26: GANTT Chart Slide	28
Figure 27: Consortium Slide	28
Figure 28: Closing Slide with Partners’ Logos	29
Figure 29: Website Navigation Tree Map	30
Figure 30: Main Menu – Navigation Bar	30
Figure 31: Website Footer	31
Figure 32: Privacy Policy	32
Figure 33: Homepage - Intro	32
Figure 34: Homepage – Short Description	33
Figure 35: Homepage – Project Objectives	33
Figure 36: Homepage – Facts and Figures	33
Figure 37: Technology Introduction.....	34
Figure 38: Technology on Novel bio-based materials.....	34
Figure 39: Use Case Example	35
Figure 40: Partners Grid	35
Figure 41: Partners – Example of company/organisation presentation	36
Figure 42: Resources – News & Press Releases.....	36
Figure 43: Resources – Communication Materials	37
Figure 44: Twitter profile	38
Figure 45: Twitter Analytics	39
Figure 46: LinkedIn Profile	39
Figure 47: 1st AMBIANCE Press Release	40
Figure 48: Sections from the Newsletters.....	41
Figure 49: Social Media Plan M6-M11	42
Figure 50: Communication Activities Report	42
Figure 51: Exploitation process.....	48
Figure 52: Business Model Canvas and environment (source: https://www.strategyzer.com/)	49
Figure 54: Technology Readiness Levels.....	51
Figure 55: Exploitation Visions.....	51

List of Tables

Table 1: Target Group	11
Table 2: Communication Quantitative Indicators.....	13
Table 3: Dissemination channels.....	45
Table 4: Preliminary Exploitable Results as reported in the proposal.....	48
Table 5: Template for the ERs Characterization	54

List of Acronyms

Awareness, Interest, Desire, and Action	AIDA
Dissemination and Communication	D&C
Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication	DEC
Dissemination and Exploitation Manager	DEM
European Commission	EC
Exploitable Result	ER
European Patent Convention	EPC
Grant Agreement	GA
General Data Protection Regulation	GDPR
Intellectual properties right	IPR
Technology Readiness Level	TRL
Joint Ownership Agreement	JOA
Key Exploitable Results	KER
Made in Europe	MIE
Minutes of the meeting	MoM
Microsoft	MS
Other Exploitable Result	OER
Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results	PEDR
Research and Development	R&D

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Scope

The present document has the scope to outline the strategy and activities followed by the consortium with regards to the communication, dissemination and exploitation actions, in order to promote the project, foster the knowledge of its results and to ensure their uptake for future business opportunities. Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities all aim to help maximize the impact of Research and Innovation actions.

Abstract

This document is the first version (M12) of the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR) of AMBIANCE project. The contents of the first release include an overview of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation strategies and action plans that the consortium will follow to promote the project, to foster the knowledge of its results and to ensure their uptake for future business opportunities. Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities all aim to help maximise the impact of Research and Innovation actions. More into detail the document is structured in two sections:

- **PART 1: Communication and Dissemination Strategy.** This section outlines the objective of the communication and dissemination strategy, the target stakeholders and group that will be addressed to raise awareness of project results. The channel and tools that the consortium is adopting for communication actions are described, together with a list of KPIs that the communication strategy should meet to be efficient in spreading AMBIANCE knowledge. Among the tools described there are: the logo, the website, the social media account already set up, the press releases, and the marketing material like roll-up and posters. A description of the activities that will be carried out for Dissemination is reported with details on the first results.
- **PART 2: Exploitation Strategy.** The third chapter of the document describes the exploitation plan of AMBIANCE project. The exploitation strategy and the guidelines that the consortium will follow in terms of characterisation of the individual exploitable results, characterisation of the Key exploitable results are outlined. Furthermore, this first release of the PEDR contains a preliminary characterization of the exploitable results that the project partners have identified. However, in the next months of the project the characterization will be implemented and further investigated to go deeper in defining which can be the suitable exploitation strategies. Intellectual Property rights, Foreground IP and Background IP and all the IP claims or IPR management issues on project results will be addressed in the next release of the PEDR as well as marketing activities.

The Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation of Results will be constantly updated during the project to guarantee the quality of the implementation and several internal versions of the document will be reviewed by the project consortium. The final plan will be delivered by M48 and it will be the most critical and important deliverable for the impact of AMBIANCE and the further exploitation of its results beyond the project lifetime.

I Plan for Communication and Dissemination

Communication and dissemination (D&C) activities play an important role to increase the impact of an HEU project as both represent useful instruments to raise awareness of EU funding opportunities, explain the societal relevance of the research, support future research and innovation funding actions, facilitate the uptake of project's results to create potential business opportunities for new products or services.

The boundaries between communication and dissemination are often blurry and sometimes overlap depending on the content to be transmitted and the target group addressed. The main aspects that differentiate these actions are their **aim, focus, and target audience**. While communication aims to create awareness of the EU initiatives, promote the project and its results to a differentiated audience - ranging from stakeholders and investors to the media and general public - dissemination is focused more on fostering the transfer of knowledge created within the project to make results available for specific users. The target audience for a dissemination action is primarily represented by the scientific community, industrial partners, and policymakers which usually have specific research, commercial and political interest in the solutions being developed in a project. In the following sub-sections, both the communication and dissemination strategies of AMBIANCE project are detailed.

I.1 Key messages

Starting from the main objectives of the project and its expected results, in terms of benefits and significance for the target audience, the key messages for the D&C need to be identified. Key messages can be expressed in a single statement or in a series of statements. They are important because they help to focus on what is being disseminated and communicated, thereby they reduce the possibility of mixed messages.

When developing key messages, it is important to keep in mind:

- The audience's current awareness, knowledge, and attitudes towards the issue.
- The response expected from the target audience/s (e.g., are you educating or informing, seeking to change attitudes or behaviours?).
- The benefits offered, and their significance.

It is also important to recognize that there is a limit to the number of messages which can be communicated, and often a trade-off between the number and complexity of key messages and the level of uptake achieved. The message is the extreme synthesis of what the project wants to communicate, or rather the essential core of the contents or line of reasoning that should, in any case, be learned and remembered by the receiver: everything, in the communication, must contribute to getting it through to the public. Messages should be based on what that audience wants to know, rather than on what they should hear. The style and content should be tailored for each audience. In order to be effective, the message must consider the objectives but, above all, the public's needs. Good communication strategies should always have key messages to be delivered in a campaign. The messages must be short, but at the same time capture the essential themes of a promotion or an intervention.

Particular attention should be given to possible incomprehension or misunderstandings. In fact, the message must be brief and clear, but not generic. In defining the message, it is important to make an effort to go beyond the initial hypotheses that come to mind, remembering above all who you are addressing.

Based on AMBIANCE objectives, a preliminary key message has been identified:

AMBIANCE will generate bio-based substitutes for traditional high-carbon products commonly employed in urban outdoor applications.

This key message will be sent to the different target audiences at appropriate precision levels and be supported by other messages. These support key messages will be spread throughout the project implementation and will be the following:

- Key message 1: AMBIANCE will reduce the environmental impact of durable products by leveraging novel bio-based materials;
- Key message 2: AMBIANCE will manufacture cost-effective, high-performance products with 100% bio-based material content;

- Key message 3: AMBIANCE will enhance manufacturing processes and quality of bio-based products by combining experimental approach and digital tools;
- Key message 4: AMBIANCE will showcase successful manufacturing processes and durable bio-based products for sustainable cities;
- Key message 5: AMBIANCE will accelerate uptake of bio-based products through upskilling and standardization.

1.2 Target audience

The overall aim of AMBIANCE D&C activities is to ensure the reach-out of the society and promote the impact and benefits of EU funded projects in a strategic and effective manner. Therefore, communication actions target stakeholders and groups covering the full range of potential users in manufacturing value chains as well as industrial and R&D communities. Each communication activity is tailored to the specific group and the message to be conveyed:

- Business and industrial actors;
- European/international associations and clusters;
- Industrial research communities, EFFRA and MIE (Made in Europe) research communities, standardization bodies;
- Other international societies and umbrella organizations;
- Citizens.

The preliminary DEC strategy, reported in the AMBIANCE proposals, reported the following target group, listed in Table 1. For each group, the D&C goals and objectives have been detailed in this first PEDR version. Based on the objectives, a dedicated D&C strategy will be developed for each targets, using the media judged more relevant with AMBIANCE

Target Groups	Specific Targets	D&C goals	Objectives
Policy Makers & Regulators	European Institutions Local Administrations Regulatory Authorities	Enhance project visibility. Create market opportunities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the awareness about AMBIANCE scope and results; • Enhance the dialogue among stakeholders to promote the correct implementation of bio-based solutions • Narrow the gap between the policy and needs for the market uptake for bio-based solutions
Citizens	Young, future professionals	Enhance project visibility. Give feedback on project development.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the awareness about AMBIANCE scope and results; • Promote the knowledge of sustainable solutions in future professionals
	General public	Enhance project visibility.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the awareness about AMBIANCE scope and results;
	Press & Media	Enhance project visibility. Create market opportunities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the awareness about AMBIANCE scope and results; • Promote AMBIANCE solutions for their future commercialization
Scientific community	Research Centres and University Scientists,	Give feedback on project development. Foster collaboration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share the generate knowledge in AMBIANCE to support future developments • Get access to future collaboration/ fundings to fully deploy AMBIANCE results
Supply chain for bio-based products manufacturing	Resource suppliers	Enhance project visibility. Create market opportunities. Foster collaboration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the awareness about AMBIANCE scope and results; • Share the generate knowledge in AMBIANCE to support future developments

	Materials suppliers	Enhance project visibility. Give feedback on project development. Create market opportunities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the awareness about AMBIANCE scope and results; • Share the generate knowledge in AMBIANCE to support future developments • Generate engagement for joint ventures for further development of bio-based materials
	Industrial companies	Enhance project visibility. Give feedback on project development. Create market opportunities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the awareness about AMBIANCE scope and results; • Generate engagement for joint ventures for further developments of bio-based solutions • Promote AMBIANCE solutions for their future commercialization
	Associations	Enhance project visibility. Create market opportunities. Foster collaboration.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the awareness about AMBIANCE scope and results; • Narrow the gap between the policy and needs for the market uptake for bio-based solutions • Promote AMBIANCE solutions for their future commercialization

Table 1: Target Group

1.3 Timeline

The timeline, which runs through the communication and dissemination activities, is structured in four stages, following the AIDA model (Awareness, Interest, Desire, and Action). The AIDA Model defines the cognitive stages that an individual goes through when making a decision. It is a model used by various organisations and is suitable for attracting and building stakeholder relations. The phases that the Dissemination & Communication strategy will follow are:

Awareness | Initial Phase | M1 – M9

Build awareness and attract the audience: During the first months of the project, communication efforts are focused on raising awareness about AMBIANCE. At this point, making the project visible and recognisable, and sharing its objectives, values, and technical innovations, are the top priorities. To that extent, the spotlight turns on creating the project’s website and social media accounts, which are essential for building a network/ community and reaching out to the first stakeholders and target audiences.

Interest | 1st Intermediate Phase | M10 – M24

Create interest among the target audience to know more about the project: In this phase, the focus shifts to raising interest by deploying the communication tools created during the initial awareness phase. Towards the end of the project’s first year (May 2023), AMBIANCE will start producing and delivering its first results. Thus, the dissemination actions will be increased in collaboration with the partners, and the project will start reaching more people. Consequently, more people will search for it and be interested in learning more about its activities. Publications and scientific papers in journals will be targeted as desired actions since researchers and scientific communities will also increase their interest in AMBIANCE. Project results will be presented at conferences, with the support and contribution of the consortium, according to the partners’ specific fields of expertise and interest. Communication actions will continue leveraging the potential of the project’s website, social media, and newsletters. Communicating and collaborating with projects under the same topic is another vital pursuit during this phase.

Desire | 2nd Intermediate Phase | M25 – M36

Create a desire to know more about the project and its results: This phase will focus on the further engagement of the targeted audiences with the project. As the project results mature and evolve, dissemination efforts are enhanced, by pursuing more event participations and publications, building up the interest in AMBIANCE and the developments achieved with the project. Informing target markets about the technological breakthroughs and business benefits of AMBIANCE is another integral part of this phase, functioning as a preparatory stage for the final mature phase. Finally, social media, website, and newsletters

continue to be vital channels for the project’s communication activities, while fostering further dialogue and collaboration with projects under the same topic.

Action | Strategic Phase | M37 – M48

Action for the interested audiences to get involved: Last, the strategic phase focuses on maximising awareness about the AMBIANCE concepts, designs, innovations, and exploitable results. Since this is the project’s final stage, all results will be disseminated through the project’s channels. Communication and dissemination efforts will be centred towards supporting the project’s sustainability and effective exploitation, and preparing its market uptake. All efforts made in the previous phases will be leveraged in this final stage.

The time factor is a core element for setting up an efficient strategy in the AIDA framework. Communication and dissemination activities will be laid out throughout the project’s duration in accordance with the progress achieved at each stage. Thus, dissemination activities will intensify and become more impactful as soon as the project sustainably produces results. The AIDA model is presented below, as adjusted to the duration and planning of AMBIANCE.

Figure 1: AIDA Model

2 Communication strategy

2.1 Introduction

Task 5.1, ‘Communication’, is led by CORE IC, coordinating, and supervising all respective activities. CORE IC is responsible for drafting and implementing the communication strategy of AMBIANCE. Nevertheless, all partners should actively contribute to the communication tasks according to their role by means of sharing input about their progress, participating in events, organising workshops, publishing papers, and disseminating the project’s results.

Communication

“Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange¹.”

Thus, communication activities include all the actions that aim to make the project visible, recognisable, and credible, to deliver its impact and benefits to society and promote it to a broader audience.

2.2 Objectives

The communication strategy of AMBIANCE aims at reaching the following goals:

- To create the project’s branding and all aesthetic elements, which will accompany the project’s communication throughout its duration and contribute towards highlighting AMBIANCE’s unique visual identity.
- To create the tools required for further dissemination of the project.
- To raise public awareness about the project, its progress, expected results and impact within well-defined target groups and,
- To make the project a valid source of information.

2.3 Communication Matrix

The materials to be created for communication purposes within AMBIANCE, are concisely presented in the matrix below:

Table 2: Communication Quantitative Indicators

Communication Material & Channels	KPIs
Project Documentation	
Leaflet	One initial version and update will be explored.
Poster	One initial version and update will be explored.
Banner	One initial version and update will be explored.
General Presentation of the Project	One initial version and update will be explored.
Project Materials	
Press Releases	At least 2 per year

¹ Source: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>

Newsletters	1 per semester
Deliverables	See the list of deliverables.
Videos	1 per use case, 3 in total
Templates	One initial version and update will be explored.
Channels	
Website	One website, monthly updated
LinkedIn	500 followers
Twitter	500 followers

3 Communication Activities and Channels

3.1 Visual Identity

Building a distinctive, dynamic, and timeless visual identity is of great importance when planning the communication strategy of an EU project. The logo should stand out, leave a powerful first impression and be memorable as the basis of the project's identity. In this regard, our effort was directed towards landing on the right concept for the logo while considering all the main elements, technologies, and aspects of the project. As a result, two logos were designed, each emphasising different project aspects, but both illustrating circularity as a core value of AMBIANCE (see figures below).

Figure 2: Logo Option 1

Figure 3: Logo Option 2

Partners were asked to vote digitally on which logo version they preferred. The first option was chosen to represent the project after receiving the most votes from the partners. The voting results can be found in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Logo Poll Results

3.1.1 Logotype Design

The proposal was analysed in depth for the logo design to identify and prioritise the key concepts and technologies. This process highlighted sustainable manufacturing, smart urban applications, and, most importantly, the circular economy, which were then incorporated into the logo design, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Logo Design Elements

3.1.2 Logo Styles

Furthermore, the design is focused on adaptability; thus, different background colours, dark or light, were considered while designing the logo styles shown below in Figure 6.

Figure 6: AMBIANCE Logo Styles

3.1.3 AMBIANCE Colour Scheme

The project's colour scheme consists mainly of green hues to highlight the lively character of the project and harmonise with its environmental aspect. Additionally, a series of three-toned-down blue-grey colours is proposed to complement the vibrant primary palette and be used as background in presentations, the project's website, and other applications. Finally, a pale red was added to the palette to function as a contrast colour.

Figure 7: Project's Colour Palette

3.1.4 Typography

Typography is an essential part of the visual identity of AMBIANCE. In this respect, for the logo and print materials, the *Helvetica Neue* and *San Francisco Pro* typefaces were chosen to convey clarity and emphasise the modern innovations of the project. Both fonts look friendly while sophisticated and are easy to read. For the project's website, we opted for the *Aktiv Grotesque* Typeface. It is a flexible and diverse font which can be applied successfully on various screen sizes and caters to a clean and contemporary look. For the templates, universally available fonts were used to ensure a seamless adaptation of the visual identity typography from all partners while ensuring that the integrity of the message is maintained.

Helvetica Neue Helvetica Neue Bold

Nulla vestibulum eleifend nulla. Suspendisse potenti. Aliquam turpis nisi, venenatis non, accumsan nec, imperdiet laoreet, lacus. In purus est, mattis eget, imperdiet nec, fermentum congue, tortor. Aenean ut nibh. Nullam hendrerit viverra dolor. Vestibulum fringilla, lectus id viverra malesuada, enim mi adipiscing ligula, et bibendum lacus lectus id sem. Cras risus turpis, varius ac, feugiat id, faucibus vitae, massa. Nunc gravida nonummy felis. Etiam suscipit, est sit amet suscipit sodales, est neque suscipit erat, nec

San Francisco Pro San Francisco Pro Bold

Nulla vestibulum eleifend nulla. Suspendisse potenti. Aliquam turpis nisi, venenatis non, accumsan nec, imperdiet laoreet, lacus. In purus est, mattis eget, imperdiet nec, fermentum congue, tortor. Aenean ut nibh. Nullam hendrerit viverra dolor. Vestibulum fringilla, lectus id viverra malesuada, enim mi adipiscing ligula, et bibendum lacus lectus id sem. Cras risus turpis, varius ac, feugiat id, faucibus vitae, massa. Nunc gravida nonummy felis. Etiam suscipit, est sit amet suscipit sodales, est neque suscipit erat, nec suscipit sem enim eget leo. In porttitor

Figure 8: Communication Materials Font

Aktiv Grotesque

Aktiv Grotesque Bold

Nulla vestibulum eleifend nulla. Suspendisse potenti. Aliquam turpis nisi, venenatis non, accumsan nec, imperdiet laoreet, lacus. In purus est, mattis eget, imperdiet nec, fermentum congue, tortor. Aenean ut nibh. Nullam hendrerit viverra dolor. Vestibulum fringilla, lectus id viverra malesuada, enim mi adipiscing ligula, et bibendum lacus lectus id sem. Cras risus turpis, varius ac, feugiat id, faucibus vitae, massa. Nunc gravida nonummy felis. Etiam suscipit, est sit amet suscipit sodales, est neque suscipit erat, nec

Figure 9: Website Font

3.1.5 Design Elements and Illustrations

To enhance the visual identity of the project and facilitate the understanding of the various technologies and innovations deployed, icons and diagrams were designed using the project's colour palette. These design elements will be used on the project's website, communication materials and presentations where and when needed. As shown in the examples below, illustrations were designed to visualize the various procedures and technologies of the project (Figure 10) and the project's concept (Figure 11).

Figure 10: Icons in dark background

Figure 11: Visualisation of the project's concept

3.2 Communication Materials

Within the first six months of AMBIANCE, communication materials were developed to support the communication and dissemination activities. The materials created so far are the following:

- the leaflet;
- the poster;
- the banner.

The above will be updated, if and when needed, according to the evolving needs and progress of the project.

Due to environmental considerations and for easier updates, AMBIANCE will mostly rely on electronic information channels. Nevertheless, printed information remains the principal means for informing specific stakeholder groups (e.g., participants in fairs, conferences, and workshops), thus print-ready documents were created as well.

The first version of the communication materials has already been distributed to the partners and uploaded to the project's website. Furthermore, the visuals created for the communication material are also uploaded separately to the project's repository for the partners' convenience.

Partners will also deploy other actions to aid the project's dissemination. Depending on the needs that may arise, other materials could be created, such as technical posters, videos, or delegate packs at conferences or other events.

3.2.1 Leaflet

An A5 leaflet was created to highlight the key aspects of the project. The brochure follows the information structure of the website. It includes a brief description of the project along with the project's concept illustration, as shown in Figure 11, to aid comprehension of the project's concept. A concise presentation of the project's Use Cases is also included, as well as its expected impact. On the final pages, the reader will find a short presentation of the Consortium, contact information for the project and information about its social media presence.

Figure 12: Leaflet Front Cover 1/5

Figure 13: Leaflet – Project & Impact 2/5

The Future of Manufacturing in Circularity

WWW.AMBIANCE-PROJECT.EU

Use Cases.

Artificial Grass Pitch

This demonstrator aims to reduce the environmental impact of artificial turf, by using bio-based materials which are recyclable, compostable or can offer recirculation alternatives.

MONDO

Urban Outdoor Furniture

SETGA will test the feasibility of large-scale 3D printing production of outdoor furniture, using recyclable biobased polymers optimised with additives for higher performance.

SETGA

Construction Bricks and Decorative Panels

PODCOMP aims to explore the manufacturing of bio-based construction bricks and decorative panels composed solely of agricultural side streams.

PODCOMP

Figure 14: Leaflet – Use Cases 3/5

The Future of Manufacturing in Circularity

WWW.AMBIANCE-PROJECT.EU

Partners.

The Consortium is composed by 10 partners across 6 European countries.

RI SE

PODCOMP

RECENDT

SUPSI

COREIC

ITAINNOVA

aimen

MONDO

SETGA

crit

Figure 15: Leaflet – Consortium 4/5

Figure 16: Leaflet – Back Cover 5/5

3.2.2 Poster and Banner

An A3 poster and an 800x2000mm banner (portrait) were additionally designed, carrying the project's visual identity on two larger-scale formats. Their main purpose is to strengthen the project's visual identity and to communicate information with a glance from a distance. For this reason, these two formats carry fewer details and aim to highlight and convey only the key aspects of the project. The Consortium members and the EU funding emblem were included in both the poster and banner along with the project's communication channels for anyone interested in learning more.

Figure 17: Poster

Figure 18: Banner

3.3 Templates

To make sure that all the materials produced within the project’s spec will be integrated and aligned with the visual identity of AMBIANCE, templates were created for the main project documents (deliverables, meeting agenda and MoMs) and presentations.

3.3.1 Deliverable

The template created for the project’s deliverables, includes styles for headings, body text, tables, and figures, as well as captions and different text highlight options. On the top of every page, a header shows the title of

the deliverable and the project’s logo. At the bottom of every page, there is a footer including the project’s acronym, Grant Agreement number as well as page number. The elements described above are showcased in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Deliverables Template

3.3.2 Agenda

Moving on to the agenda template, styles for headings, tables, and captions were included. The project’s logo, title and the name of the meeting were included in the first page of the agenda. Furthermore, at the bottom of each page, there is a footer with the EU funding emblem. All the elements described above, can be seen in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Agenda Template

3.3.3 Minutes of Meeting

The Minutes of Meeting template contains heading, body text, table, and caption styles. A header with the meeting name and project logo appears at the top of each page. There is a footer with the EU funding emblem at the bottom of each page, followed by the paging. The above elements can be found in Figure 21.

Figure 21: Minutes of Meeting Template (MoM)

3.3.4 Presentation

The presentation template was set up according to the same philosophy as the rest of the templates, embodying the visual identity of AMBIANCE by including styles for headings, body text and other visual elements while making the most out of the project’s colour palette. The template has been created in a 16:9 widescreen format to make it suitable for all screen types. The primary goal was to produce a creative template that would brighten and spark AMBIANCE’s presentations. The figures below demonstrate examples of the PowerPoint presentation slides in light and dark colour schemes.

Figure 22: Presentation’s Title Slide with Light Background

Figure 23: Presentation’s Title Slide with Dark Background

Figure 24: Work Package Description Slide

Figure 25: Transitional Slide

Figure 26: GANTT Chart Slide

Figure 27: Consortium Slide

Figure 28: Closing Slide with Partners' Logos

3.4 Website

Undoubtedly, a strong online presence can be key to maximising the effectiveness of the project's message and its reach. The website is the main Communication and Dissemination tool for any European project and its fundamental way of reaching out to external stakeholders and the wider public. A well-structured website guarantees that project-related details are communicated to end-users, project outcomes are disseminated and promoted as far as possible, and, last but not least, the community of interested parties is enlarged, ensuring the project's sustainability.

In the early phase of the project, launching a modern and sophisticated website, which reflects AMBIANCE's fundamental values was a priority. To support the website launch and expand the project's reach, the team also focused on establishing social media channels.

CORE IC designed and developed the website as well as created and edited its content, drawing from the project's proposal. The website will be dynamic and continuously evolving, updated on a regular basis with the latest project details that are available to the general audience. This comprises project-specific material as well as public documents that can be downloaded, such as brochures, working papers, presentations, and reports. Along with newsletters and press releases, news and events such as workshops, seminars, and conferences will be published. Finally, input will be provided by and in collaboration with the other project partners throughout the whole duration of the project.

The first edition of the website was released on M4 of the project (September 2022).

3.4.1 Website Structure

AMBIANCE's website is accessible at: <https://www.ambiance-project.eu/>.

All website pages bear the project's logo on the top left, links to the project's social media, and a prompt for the newsletter subscription on the top right.

The website's footer is a consistent design element through all pages of the website. Each page's footer contains the EU funding emblem, the project's GA number, the contact details of the Project Coordinator, and of course a link to the Privacy Policy.

Links to the main pages "Home", "Technology", "Use Cases", "Partners", and "Resources" ("News & Press Releases", "Communication Material", "Project Deliverables") are included in the navigation bar, which is accessible from all sub-pages.

Figure 29: Website Navigation Tree Map

3.4.2 Essential Technical Features

While building the website, creating a mobile-friendly and responsive design was a top concern. CORE IC attempted to apply the fundamentals of UX design by developing a modern, easy-to-navigate website with an emphasis on inclusiveness and usability.

The website's technological characteristics include the following:

- Complete responsiveness: all contents and pages have a mobile-ready version.
- Cross-platform/desktop/browser compatibility: the website is compatible with the main five browsers.

3.4.3 Aesthetic Elements

Overall, the website has a simple layout, where each page is dedicated on a different core aspect of the project. The use of illustrations, photos, and distinct background colours helps in the arrangement of each page, facilitates the comprehension of the innovation pursued and increases awareness of the project's visual identity. Most photos used are royalty-free, and were chosen to complement the accompanying text and improve its understanding with visual cues. In the "Use Cases" page, the uploaded photos were provided by the responsible partners.

In the text subsections, the background colour is predominately white, while dark backgrounds are used in some subsections that display technical data to highlight the respective content. Pop-up panes are occasionally used to keep the content brief and fit it onto a single computer screen, helping visitors keep track of their navigation on the site.

3.4.4 Main Pages

Main Menu - Navigation Bar

As displayed in the following figure, the website content is divided into five main sections.

Figure 30: Main Menu – Navigation Bar

The navigation bar on the top of the browser and allows easy and immediate access to the entire website with links to the following pages:

1. **Home:** The homepage offers an overview of the project’s purpose, and its objectives, as well as some facts and figures. It will eventually be complemented with a news section, displaying the latest updates of AMBIANCE.
2. **Technology:** ‘Technology’ contains a more detailed explanation of the technologies deployed in AMBIANCE. Particularly, it comprises of a brief explanation of the project’s concept, followed by a presentation of the novel bio-based materials optimisation and characterisation techniques, as well as the manufacturing processes optimisation.
3. **Use Cases:** This section elaborates on the three demonstration sites where the solution developed in AMBIANCE will be put to the test.
4. **Partners:** A presentation of all partners who participate in the project, including a short description of the organisation/company, a logo, and a link to their website.
5. **Resources:** This cluster of pages provides updates about the course of the project and important resource material for different purposes. It consists of the following subpages:

News & Press Releases: This page connects the project with the audience by communicating all the latest developments through published newsletters, press releases, the project’s Twitter feed etc.

Communication Material: This page provides quick access to the Communication Material of the project, like the logo kit, posters, flyers etc.

Project Deliverables: This page is dedicated to presenting an archive of AMBIANCE’s public deliverables.

Footer Section

The main elements of the footer area include the official EU funding emblem and the project’s Grant Agreement number. Furthermore, a link to the Privacy Policy is included, and by clicking it, the user is redirected to a dedicated page (see Figure 32), where they can read an extended text that describes the privacy policy, collection of personal data, tracking technologies and cookies, GDPR, etc., on the website. Last but not least, along with the contact details of the Project Coordinator, ITAINNOVA, there is a mention of the website designer, CORE IC. The footer is displayed in the figure below:

Figure 31: Website Footer

Figure 32: Privacy Policy

Home

The user's first experience with the website is a pop-up displaying the cookies policy. In this pop-up, the user can pick whether to allow only necessary cookies, a selection of cookies, or all cookies. The pop-up disappears after the user clicks the button of their choice.

The Homepage begins with the project logo and its full title. Additionally, it provides a link to the newsletter subscription form and the project’s social media accounts.

Figure 33: Homepage - Intro

Under the same section, users can find a brief description of the project and its main concept in a concise paragraph to maintain the audience’s interest without displaying too much information all at once.

Figure 34: Homepage – Short Description

In the same section, the project’s objectives are presented underneath the introductory text, as shown in Figure 35.

Figure 35: Homepage – Project Objectives

Lastly, a brief and boldly displayed list of the project’s facts and figures about the Consortium members, duration, and funding is completing the homepage. This is one of the instances where the use of a different background colour emphasizes the content and, with visual cues, divides the various sections of the page.

Figure 36: Homepage – Facts and Figures

Technology

Technology

A mix of experimental activities and digital approaches will be used to improve bio-based composite materials and manufacturing processes and create a life cycle model of each manufacturing value chain.

This model will provide useful information for the design of the bio-based product and facilitate its further refurbishment and remanufacturing. Simultaneously, it will assist the **optimisation of manufacturing processes** with feedback on materials, machine, and process parameters.

By utilising novel digital-based circularity concepts, AMBIANCE will **extend the life cycle of bio-based products** and increase their robustness against environmental and production changes.

Figure 37: Technology Introduction

As an introduction to the "Technology" page, a concise description of the concept and the main technologies that will be developed were used. The audience is briefly introduced to the approaches that will power the project's endeavour. The text is accompanied by the project's concept visualisation (Figure 11).

Moving on, the different project pillars, novel bio-based materials and manufacturing processes optimisation, are analysed in depth, as indicated in Figure 38.

Novel bio-based materials

The development and optimisation will be achieved, following 2 alternative courses:

1 By **using modifiers to enhance material properties**. Different experiment designs will allow to assert the optimum formulation of the material. At the same time, simulation and data analysis will attribute in the assessment and optimisation of the material's characteristics.

2 By **processing agricultural side streams** to create innovative self-bonded bio-based material.

Material Optimisation Techniques

Design of Experiments (DoE) – To achieve the required material properties, countless experiments must be carried out with all possible parameters affecting the mechanical properties of the material. For that reason, experiments will be combined with statistical techniques in a Design of Experiment approach, to accelerate the production of results.

Molecular Dynamics (MD) – This simulation tool will be used to predict the biobased material properties and the mechanical and thermal properties of the biobased composite materials.

Figure 38: Technology on Novel bio-based materials

Use Cases

The solutions developed within the spec of AMBIANCE, will be showcased, and integrated in three demonstration sites; sport facilities, outdoor furniture and construction bricks and decorative panels. For each of the demonstrators, there is a small description of the procedure and a relevant image provided by the responsible partner. Additionally, there is a distinct section in each demonstrator which displays the resulting benefits of each use case.

Use Case 2

Outdoor Furniture

This demonstrator will focus on large-scale manufacturing of 3d printed outdoor furniture using recycled materials.

The aim of Setga is to test the feasibility of such large-scale 3d printing production, using recyclable biobased polymers optimised with additives for higher performance. The end products should be able to endure any weather conditions and human-related factors as well as feature an attractive design responding to various end-user needs.

The manufacturing facility for this use case consists of an LSAM (Large Scale Additive Manufacturing) robot cell. Real time temperature 3D mapping generation through a thermographic camera, to assist the printing process, will be developed and embedded in the robot cell.

The Benefits

- Better endurance of materials against climate and human factors.
- Better recyclability and biodegradability properties.
- Reduce of lifecycle costs.

Figure 39: Use Case Example

Partners

The purpose of this sub-page is to present all members of the Consortium. The partners are displayed in a simple grid format, featuring their the company/organisations’ logos arranged in the same order they are listed in the project’s Grant Agreement, as shown in Figure 40.

Partners

The Consortium is composed by **10** partners across 6 European countries.

Figure 40: Partners Grid

By clicking on the logo, a white pop-up window will emerge displaying a brief introduction of the correspondent company/organisation, along with a link to their website, as shown in the example below.

Figure 41: Partners – Example of company/organisation presentation

Resources

This page serves as a point of contact with the audience since it is the most regularly updated page, providing the most recent news, relevant links, communication materials, and public project deliverables. As the project evolves, this page will be more regularly updated with ‘fresh’ content.

News & Press Releases

As the project progresses and the respective communication and dissemination activities intensify, this page will feature networking events, fairs, workshops, conferences, and exhibitions. The audience can browse through a carousel displaying the project’s news, a calendar of project-related events, a list of published press releases and newsletters arranged chronologically, and a Twitter feed that shows the latest updates posted on Twitter.

Figure 42: Resources – News & Press Releases

Communication Material

On this subpage, users can have access to the Communication Material of the project. This material consists of files of the project’s logo and the ready-to-print versions of the leaflet, poster, and banner.

Figure 43: Resources – Communication Materials

Project Deliverables

All submitted deliverables with public dissemination level will be available for download in pdf format from this subpage.

3.5 Social Media

The first step in establishing the communication channels of AMBIANCE was to set up the social media accounts, with the aim of raising awareness among interested stakeholders and maintaining public engagement. AMBIANCE will engage in different social media profiles, pages and online communities based on the project topics, which include advanced manufacturing, novel bio-based materials and circularity.

CORE IC will oversee the project's social media activities, including managing social media accounts and their performance, and responding to direct messages. To comply with the Horizon Europe guidelines "Communicating about your EU-funded project," social media communication will follow a specific approach of updating social networks regularly, by joining groups and approaching individuals interested in the project topics, sharing relevant content, retweeting, and sharing official updates from the EC, its other Horizon EU channels, and other projects.

Furthermore, the project partners will utilise their established social media channels to effectively disseminate the project's activities and results to the intended audiences. CORE IC has developed a social media methodology which focuses on cultivating trust and sharing knowledge through high-quality content, utilising added-value content from project processes and first-hand involvement, and employing an integrated approach to communication actions across different platforms.

To select the most suitable media and platforms, the CORE IC team will analyse when and where the target audiences are most engaged online. The project website will host official project information, while other channels will be used to approach target audiences and disseminate content in a more targeted manner. LinkedIn is the ideal medium to connect the project with the research community and Twitter will tone up engagement with stakeholders with its capsule project updates. To that extent, a detailed social media plan has been drafted towards increasing the digital footprint of the project.

The social media plan includes guidelines for using hashtags and mentions to increase interaction between partners, organisations, companies, and European and national bodies involved in the Horizon Europe framework. The hashtag #HorizonEU, the official hashtag of the EC for the Horizon Europe framework, will be included in all public posts on LinkedIn and Twitter, and other mentions and hashtags will vary depending

on the context of the content and the partner/organization involved. The use of these platforms will enhance the impact of the project's communication activities and increase awareness and online presence.

3.5.1 Twitter

A Twitter account was created upon the beginning of the project. Since the website launched on M4, this account has been actively sharing content, articles and news related to the project.

Figure 44: Twitter profile

To better monitor AMBIANCE Twitter account's activity and impact, the Twitter Analytics tool is used (Figure 45). So far, Twitter Analytics demonstrate a satisfying performance when it comes to followers, engagement, and impressions.

Figure 45: Twitter Analytics

3.5.2 LinkedIn

On M1, a LinkedIn account was created to reach a more professional audience, the academic and scientific community, the industry actors, and other interested stakeholders (Figure 46). LinkedIn will be used as a complementary tool to the website, with regular updates regarding the progress of AMBIANCE. Overall, the posts reflect the gradual increase of project activities and at the same time enhance the number of followers. Last, all consortium members have been invited to connect with the project’s LinkedIn account and are urged to interact with the updates.

Figure 46: LinkedIn Profile

3.5.3 Other Accounts

A Google account (ambiance.project.eu@gmail.com) has been created to manage the social media of the project. This account can also be used for future project communication, if such need appears.

A YouTube account will be launched once the first project video is created. Video has proven to be a more effective method undoubtedly engage more people with the project. AMBIANCE will create one video production per use case and could further deploy the power of video with small productions such as interviews from the industry actors and other interesting actions towards the project's promotion.

3.6 Press Releases

As part of AMBIANCE's communication strategy, periodic press releases coinciding with major project meetings and events are published. They are published when there is progress to report or when a significant project event is about to occur. Press releases are shared in the same way as newsletters, through AMBIANCE's website and social media accounts, with the goal of engaging traditional and digital media and specific target groups with our project's achievements and milestones.

Partners are encouraged to share the project's press releases through their established networks and channels to amplify the message and maximise the reach and dissemination impact. The first press release of the project was published on M4 (September 2022) and is available for downloading through the AMBIANCE website. It was also announced and shared through the project's social media accounts (Twitter and LinkedIn).

ambiance

Advanced Manufacturing of Biobased products for urban outdoor applications through iNnovative CharactERisation, digital technologies, and circular approach.

Our Project Kicked Off | June 2022

On the 2nd of June 2022, the kick-off meeting of AMBIANCE took place online with the participation of all members of the Consortium. In this e-meeting coordinated by ITAINNOVA, the partners had the chance to introduce to each other and have an interesting discussion about the project's objectives, ambitions, work packages as well as the upcoming actions.

ABOUT AMBIANCE

AMBIANCE aims at developing novel biobased products for urban outdoor applications through innovative characterisation, digital technologies, and circular approach.

By promoting sustainable manufacturing models, optimising the manufacturing processes in the above applications, and ensuring the replicability of the results, the higher aim of AMBIANCE is to reduce the environmental impact and make sustainable and recyclable products a norm in European cities.

The project will rely on combining advanced experimental activities and digital approaches to improve biobased composite materials and manufacturing processes and create a life cycle model of each of the manufacturing value chains at hand.

The solutions developed within the spec of AMBIANCE, will be showcased, and integrated in 3 demonstration sites:

- Manufacturing process of artificial grass pitches by MONDO
- Large-scale manufacturing of 3D printed outdoor furniture by SETGA
- Manufacturing of biobased construction bricks and decorative panels by PODCOMP

PARTNERS

The consortium consists of 10 partners from Austria, Greece, Italy, Spain, Sweden, and Switzerland. A group that brings together experienced and committed individuals of different disciplines, who will contribute the most towards achieving the project objectives.

ITAINNOVA aimen CRIT CORE-IC MONDO
SETGA PODCOMP RECENDT RISE SUPSI

FOR ADDITIONAL INFORMATION PLEASE CONTACT

Project Coordinator: ITAINNOVA
Genma Ibarz Ric gibarz@itainnova.es
Communication Manager: Core Innovation Centre
Mina Tsatsani mtsatsani@core-innovation.com

FOLLOW US

Figure 47: 1st AMBIANCE Press Release

3.7 Newsletters

AMBIANCE has developed its email database and subscriber acquisition processes in full compliance with the GDPR regulations for safeguarding personal data. Taking into consideration the GDPR Privacy Policy, partners may avoid sharing the newsletter directly with their mailing list, and most of them integrate it into their organisation's newsletter.

The newsletter's content will encompass various updates on the project's progress and advancements, significant events and conferences, announcements of publications and other related media releases. The target audience comprises both the individuals involved internally with the project and those who have exhibited a significant level of engagement with AMBIANCE by subscribing through the project's website and providing active consent to receive these communications.

The newsletters are issued on the MailChimp platform. Until M12, AMBIANCE has already sent two newsletters. The 1st Newsletter was sent in November 2022 and included a brief description of the project, as well as the coordinator's note. The 2nd Newsletter was sent in March 2023, hosting the collaboration with the ENGINE Initiative and the latest project updates.

Figure 48: Sections from the Newsletters

3.8 Internal Communication Campaign

Complementing the external communication efforts, the project also implements a comprehensive internal communication campaign with the aim of engaging various dissemination channels in a coherent and robust manner. This strategy has been planned to improve efficiency, and we anticipate that our partners will distribute the materials we have created via a multitude of channels rather than limiting dissemination to just the project's official communication channels. The main objective is to ensure that reliable information is accessible from as many sources as possible, thereby broadening the project's reach. Some of the methods utilized to achieve these objectives are:

3.8.1 Social Media Plan

To increase AMBIANCE's following on social media, all partners are expected to follow the project's Twitter and LinkedIn accounts. Partners should also use their networks to promote the project by sending group messages, inviting people to follow the project's accounts, and sharing AMBIANCE's content regularly.

A Social Media Plan was developed to keep the audience engaged with interesting content. The plan has been shared with the consortium, and partners are encouraged to contribute with content related to their work, news from the sector, or updates on their progress in the field. To ensure quality, partner contributions should include both text and visual elements. The plan is updated and shared with partners every six months, assigning partners monthly to distribute the effort evenly.

	November	December	January	February	March	April
Content	Project news and progress	Project news and progress	Project news and progress	Project news and progress	Project news and progress	Project news and progress
Partner	ITA AIMEN CRIT CORE	CORE MONDO SETGA CORE	PODCOMP RECENTDT RISE CORE	SUPSI ITA AIMEN CORE	CRIT CORE MONDO CORE	SETGA PODCOMP RECENTDT CORE

Figure 49: Social Media Plan M6-M11

3.8.2 Reporting Forms

To better keep track of the project communication-related activities, a reporting form was created using Microsoft Forms. Partners can report any communication activities relevant to the project (newsletters, social media posts, website articles, videos etc.) without having a Microsoft account.

The form is accessible through the following link: [Communication Activities Report](#).

Figure 50: Communication Activities Report

4 Dissemination strategy

4.1 Introduction

The article 17 of the Annotated Model Grant Agreement clearly states that “The beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, subject to any restrictions due to the protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests.”. The article not only states an obligation but provides also the definition of dissemination that in wider terms means “spreading something, especially information, as far as possible”. As previously mentioned, the fine line between communication and dissemination actions is often a blurry boundary that sometimes fades depending on the content to be transmitted and target group.

Compared to communication, dissemination activities are more focused on results and solutions deriving from a project. Thus, the objective is not only to create awareness, but also to describe the results and the solutions to ensure understanding and enable others to use and take up results. Scientific communities, industrial partners and policymakers are the audiences addressed by dissemination activities since they are considered the most interested in the use of the solutions provided by the project.

Therefore, the goal of transferring knowledge and results to the ones that can best use them makes the dissemination a key activity to maximize the impact of a project: it ensures the possibility to use the project outputs beyond the lifetime of the project and to broaden their value compared to the original focus.

There are several benefits deriving from a good dissemination strategy:

- Enhanced **visibility** of the project research line and drawing the attention of potential users on the project outputs;
- The gain in **credibility** within the scientific community and so the possibility to find new additional funding sources or to join new consortia;
- Occasion to learn novel approaches and solutions thanks to the **exchange of knowledge** on all levels and the cross-fertilization of ideas.

4.2 AMBIANCE dissemination strategy

Task 5.2 is dedicated to dissemination activities and led by CRIT. The scope of the task is to develop and manage a reliable dissemination strategy to generate awareness of AMBIANCE results in both the academic and professional communities. The main objective of the AMBIANCE dissemination strategy is to identify and plan the activities to be performed to transfer the findings and the results of the project and develop a response mechanism between the consortium and the various stakeholders to maximize the impact of AMBIANCE. More in detail, this translates in a series of milestones:

- the creation of **public awareness** on the project,
- the generation of **interest** within the scientific community,
- the direct involvement of **stakeholders** that can facilitate market up-take of research results.

To ensure the effectiveness of the strategy and the accomplishments of the fixed goals, dissemination is meant to be performed both as a collective activity managed by the entire consortium and coordinated by the Dissemination Manager (CRIT) and, at the same time, as an individual set of actions carried out by each single partner at the local level. AMBIANCE members comprise both industrial and R&D partners who are well-established organizations that constitute a natural channel for the dissemination of the project and its results to other potential users. Hence, AMBIANCE dissemination actions have relied on the vast experience, know-how and expertise of its members to ensure that projects’ output get the necessary exposure to guarantee their utilization after the project is concluded.

The plan for the dissemination activities is a dynamic process which started from outlining the Description of Action, went through the kick-off meeting discussions and will be constantly updated over the full duration of the project.

In line with the Interest and Desire phases of the D&C plan and with the aim to fulfil the dissemination and communication purposes, a constant search and further creation of a list of events and conferences that could

be relevant to AMBIANCE members and results will be performed from Year 2. This list will be monitored and periodically updated and shared with the members throughout the whole period.

AMBIANCE dissemination actions not only comply with Article 17 of the Grant Agreement, but also with Section 8.4 of the Consortium Agreement that specifically regulates the dissemination of owned (or jointly owned) results restricted to publications and presentations as follow “Prior notice of any planned dissemination shall be given to the other Parties at least 30 calendar days before the intended activity, such as publication or presentations, providing a copy of the relevant material at least with 15 calendar days before the intended activity, unless explicitly agreed other deadlines in writing by the concerned Parties”.

Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the DEM, the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 15 calendar days after receipt of the notice, and 10 calendar days after receipt of the material, unless explicitly agreed other deadlines in writing by the concerned Parties. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the dissemination activity is deemed permitted, in accordance with the notice given.”

Besides the basic regulations within the Consortium Agreement and Grant Agreement, AMBIANCE dissemination management follows the best practices suggested by the EC Guidelines as well as the practices deriving from the well-established experience of the partners in other research projects:

- All the partners involved in the research activities will be made aware about the final results of the project and the implications resulting from the outputs like publications and presentations.
- All the scientific articles on the results of the project will be duly reviewed by the relevant partners involved in the development of the topic of the publication.
- All the articles and publications on project outputs will be shared within the consortium before the date of disclosure.
- All the partners should contribute to the dissemination according to their role and effort by participating and giving presentations at conferences, workshops, meetings, by publishing papers, holding press conferences, networking, and similar activities.
- The Dissemination and Exploitation Manager (DEM) is the reference and contact point for every dissemination action. He/she is in charge to constantly verify the quality of the contents to be shared, to ensure the correct implementation of the project results and the consistency between the events to be attended by the partners and the purpose of the dissemination activity.
- All public results will be accessible from the project website and the online repositories ZENODO and OpenAIRE, and freely usable from all parties who may benefit from them to maximize the impact of the project.
- The submission to Open Research Europe (<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>) will be evaluated for all the publication.

To ensure the effective fostering of AMBIANCE knowledge, the deployment of the dissemination strategy follows some milestones:

- The topic and message of the dissemination action (the contents that will be shared);
- The target audience (who are the stakeholders to be addressed and that may have more interest for the topic);
- The messenger (the messenger should be a credible spokesperson who is expert of the subject to be disseminated);
- The methods and tools (the transfer method should be carefully considered depending on the nature of the event: the size of the audience, the background of the participants and the location);
- The expected outcome (the impact to be achieved and the purpose of the dissemination must be defined to optimally deliver the message).

4.3 Dissemination Channels

To be efficient in pursuing AMBIANCE dissemination strategy, the consortium has identified the main channels to transfer the knowledge and the outcomes of the project:

Table 3: Dissemination channels

CHANNEL	SCOPE
Trade fairs and conferences	Involvement Promotion
Cluster events	Involvement Promotion
Workshops	Involvement
Journal articles	Information
Webinars	Involvement Information
Networking	Involvement Promotion

The chosen channels are efficient D&C means to foster knowledge-based economy. As reported by the World Bank: *"The increased speed in the creation and dissemination of knowledge has led to the rapid spread of modern and efficient production techniques, plus the increased probability of leapfrogging, which has consequently resulted in the world economy becoming much more competitive"*. In this content, the AMBIANCE Dissemination channels have been chosen because, in line with the project's objective, are able to create the proper spatial and relational proximity needed to boost the mutual learning and the right condition for benchmarking innovations and knowledge exchange.

A customizable questionnaire has been prepared to appropriately gather data and information related to the dissemination activities promoted by the AMBIANCE partners. The questionnaire will be proposed to the partners every 4 months, starting from M13, as an online MS forms questionnaire, fixed in the WP5 MS Teams channel in the project repository.

4.4 Clustering activities

Cluster events represent a useful channel for disseminating the knowledge produced during a project since they allow to reach widely scientific communities and industrial partners that could have a direct interest in project progress and results.

AMBIANCE project has been already included in ENGINE initiative: It was born as a voluntary initiative inside the H2020 Manusquare project and currently involves projects running under the H2020 and HEU framework, with the common perspective of fostering the sharing, dissemination and exploitation of up-to-date information about projects' results and initiatives, in order to mutually extend dissemination channels, find connection points among the participating projects, and promoting networking and cross-fertilisation in the EU based digital innovation domain.

Furthermore, clustering activities will be carried out among the project in the same topic of AMBIANCE project with the aim of generating synergies in the D&C activities and creating a roadmap for bio-based material used in manufacturing environment. The topic of AMBIANCE project is [HORIZON-CL4-2021-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-05 - Manufacturing technologies for bio-based materials \(Made in Europe Partnership\) \(RIA\)](#) and the identified projects in the same topic are:

- **BIO-UPTAKE:** BIOcomposites in smart plastic transformation processes to pave the way for the large-scale UPTAKE of sustainable bio-based products;
- **GREEN-LOOP** Sustainable manufacture systems towards novel bio-based materials
- **Waste2BioComp** Converting organic waste into sustainable bio-based components
- **NewWave** Building a sustainable & circular economy through innovative, biobased manufacturing lines
- **VITAL** InnoVatIve processing Technologies for bio-based foAmed thermopLastics

To be continuously aware of dissemination opportunities, a list of relevant regional, national and European Cluster events is constantly updated. Indeed, partners were periodically asked to list the clusters they belong to and the events they wish to attend.

4.5 Scientific Articles

In order to reach the scientific community AMBIANCE consortium promotes scientific paper publication and project presentation at scientific conferences targeting relevant domains for the project. The expected impact of presentations at these events is very high because of the attendance of scientists and industrial stakeholders.

In addition to the pure scientific papers, the results and impacts of AMBIANCE project were communicated to professionals, end-users, and industries through papers in technical bulletins and sectorial journals.

4.6 Networking with European Associations

The dissemination of AMBIANCE results will be pursued through an active participation and networking with European associations connected to the project topic.

A first collaboration has been already set up with **EFFRA**, the public-private partnership related to manufacturing. AMBIANCE project has been already uploaded to EFFRA innovation portal, an online platform for sharing information about research and innovation projects and associated project results and demonstrators in the area of manufacturing. Furthermore, the attendance of AMBIANCE to **EFFRA Manufacturing Partnership Day** (26th September 2023) has been already established. In the event, the project will be presented to the EFFRA community by 10-15 minutes presentation and a section in the exhibition area, where the consortium will display project's dissemination materials. The event will be also a good opportunity to network with the other Factories of the future and Made in Europe projects and generate further clustering possibilities.

4.6.1 Biopolymers associations

Biopolymers is a hype topic of discussion at European level. The current policies on the recycling of plastics and single-use regulation are strongly pushing for a transition towards a more sustainable use of polymers. Many associations were born to support academics and industries in this transition. The main goals of these are to share knowledge about bio-based materials, support the definition of new policies for the use of bio-based materials and aid industries to be ready for the transition from fossil to bio-based. In this contest, the association are a good chance to spread AMBIANCE results in communities already engaged in sustainable materials. A scouting will be held to identify the most suitable associations, based on AMBIANCE goals and key messages. Once the associations are identified, they will be contacted to start a potential collaboration.

5 Exploitation – General Overview

In the context of EU-funded projects, Exploitation is the part of the project that deals with the use of the results for commercial purposes or in public policymaking. It covers the identification of the results obtained during the action and their subsequent use in further research activities as well as developing, creating and marketing a process or service.

The exploitation of the results should guarantee a return on investment of the funding provided by the Commission and states the value and impact of the funded activities, whether it be commercial, societal, political or knowledge-based. Without it, the knowledge would not be shared with other consortia or the community itself, with the risk of efforts being repeated in the future. Also, the investment effort is considered as a push to allow new products, processes and services to be commercialised, creating new job opportunities and strengthening the position and competitiveness of Europe in the global market.

The importance of exploitation activities is very considerable under Horizon Europe. In that regard, it is important to clearly identify during the project execution different types of exploitable results such as methods, knowledge, communities of interest or technologies for instance. Furthermore, EU-funded projects are pushed to take into account what goes beyond the project duration by generating an exploitation plan that goes at least four years after the project.

This includes identifying the role of each partner involved, how the results will impact him and which value this will represent. The impediments towards the exploitation should be identified, whether they concern Intellectual Property, competition or certification, and the appropriate measures should be considered and applied. The pertinent protection should also be applied to the new intellectual property developed during the project, whether jointly or individually.

One key aspect to keep in mind is that, although a preliminary exploitation plan is almost always presented at the proposal stage, it should be updated during the course of the project. Actually, if the exploitation tasks are correctly performed, the initial exploitation plan should considerably change. The main reason is that the average time between the writing of the proposal and the exploitation of the results is three and a half years. In this considerable amount of time, it should be common that the initial business case is replaced by a new one.

5.1 Exploitation in AMBIANCE – Objectives and strategy

Within the AMBIANCE project, the exploitation activities are included in WP5, task 5.3. This task has two main and complementary objectives:

- To provide the exploitation strategies for project partners to take explicit advantage from the development of AMBIANCE, as they will become the founding elements for a new generation of bio-based products;
- To maximize the potential impact of the technologies developed during the project through an explicit market involvement.

At the proposal stage, a preliminary exploitation strategy, with the classification of potential exploitable results, has been identified:

Project Result	Exploited by	Individual exploitation strategies based on MULO Matrix: Lead Users (Exploitation means)
KER1: New Bio-Based Products	MONDO, SETGA, PODCOMP	MONDO, SETGA, PODCOMP (Make): <i>New bio-based products (fully recyclable and high performance) to increase the EU market share and access to new geographical and sectorial markets</i> Background IP: Patent grant: EP2899301B1
KER2: Advanced manufacturing processes	Early adopters: MONDO, SETGA, PODCOMP, ITA, AIMEN, RISE, CORE, RECENDT	MONDO, SETGA, PODCOMP (Use): <i>Improved manufacturing processes for the new bio-based products.</i> ITA, AIMEN, RISE, CORE, RECENDT (Other: service): <i>Tech transfer through licensing to</i>

		<i>manufacturing companies in different value chains for new bio-based products</i> Background IP: Know-how
OER1: Bio-based materials	ITA, AIMEN, RISE	ITA, AIMEN, RISE(Other: service): <i>New bio-based materials with enhanced properties to be integrated in new bio-based products. Tech transfer through licensing to bio-based materials developer companies.</i>
OER2: Monitoring systems	AIMEN, RECENDT	AIMEN, RECENDT (Other: service): <i>New monitoring systems to be integrated in bio-based products manufacturing processes. Tech transfer through licensing to integrators and technology providers.</i>
OER3: Data Analytics tools	CORE	CORE (Other: service): <i>New AI-based process optimisation tools to increase current market share and enter in new geographical markets. and/or gaining new customers.</i>
OER4: Simulation Models	ITA	ITA (Other: service): <i>Molecular dynamics studies on biopolymers and fillers. Tech transfer, advanced engineering service</i>

Table 4: Preliminary Exploitable Results as reported in the proposal

The overall objective of the exploitation activities is to maximise the impact of the project results so that they can be used and implemented beyond the lifetime of the project. This challenging final goal can be expressed as a list of sub-goals to be reached:

- Reach a synergic approach between communication, dissemination and exploitation in order to reach the stakeholders;
- Identify of the innovations and characterize them;
- Define how to get the expected innovations “out of the lab” and into (or at least closer to) the market and identify possible, most appropriate exploitation routes for the expected key exploitable results corresponding to the nature of the different results and their target users;
- Choose concrete exploitation measures to ensure that results will meet real needs and thus will be taken up. What are the relevant steps within the project’s lifetime and beyond?
- Reflect on potential barriers/obstacles, and how to overcome them;
- Consider including dedicated formats (workshops, questionnaires, etc.) to capture and assess exploitation opportunities in the project;
- Plan and describe adequate internal structures safeguarding effective knowledge, IP and innovation management, helping to create, capture and manage research results.

The AMBIANCE impact enhancement plan is following a strategy based on the topics listed below, in details described in the following sections:

Figure 51: Exploitation process

The exploitation activities have been designed a 5 step-process which bring the consortium to define the most appropriate roadmaps to exploit the results after the end of the project. The defined phases are:

- **IDENTIFY:** this phase is focused on the analysis and characterization of the ERs. The main objective is to increase the awareness among partners about the potential KERs and OERs and the outcomes that they can produce. In this phase a detailed characterization of the ERs will be carried out in order to collect the information need for the development of the next phases. Furthermore, the value proposition for KERs will be defined and the most interested customers segments will be identified. The early identification of customers segments allows to define specific D&C activities and generate involvement from the beginning.
- **KNOW THE COMPETITIVE ENVIRONMENT:** once the ERs have been identified, it is important to define the external factors that can influence the ERs exploitation strategy. First of all, a technology and market trends analysis is carried out to identify opportunities and obstacles in the exploitation of the ERs. Furthermore, a patent analysis is carried out to delineate the current IP scenario and define a correct IP strategy to protect the generated inventions in AMBIANCE with respect the state of the art. Attention will be paid to joint-owned results with the scope of clearly define the exploitation route among the involved partners. In the end, Porter's 5 forces analysis will be performed. Porter's 5 Forces is a model that identifies and analyses five competitive forces that shape every industry and helps determine an industry's weaknesses and strengths. The collected information will be shared with the AMBIANCE partners in order to complete the Business Model canvas and the Business Model Environment (MILESTONE 1), as reported in Figure 52.

Figure 52: Business Model Canvas and environment (source: <https://www.strategyzer.com/>)

- **MAKE THE POTENTIAL OUT:** this phase is focused on recognised advantages and barriers for the ERs exploitation. Based on the defined BMC, a SWOT analysis will be performed and using the results, an exploitation strategy will be selected. Furthermore, the BMC outputs will be used in the Value Chain Analysis to find out the correct organization's interaction with partners to produce, market, distribute and support its offerings;
- **ROAD TO THE FUTURE:** The exploitation roadmap and the financial projections will be developed based on the results of the previous phase. The definition of the value chain and development strategy will allow to define the main tasks to be carried out by the end of the project and for four years above. If a commercialization strategy will be chosen, a financial projection will be outlined. The results of this stage will be a business plan that includes the main tasks to be performed after the end of the project (MILESTONE 2).
- **IMPLEMENTATION BEYOND THE PROJECT:** This stage concerns the exploitations activities after the end of the project. The Exploitation manager (CRIT) will monitor that the defined exploitation

roadmaps will be implemented and, if not, contingency plan will be considered. If, after 1 year, some results will be not yet exploited, the consortium will upload them in the Horizon Results Platform, following the principle “as open as possible, as close as needed”. Furthermore, the coordinator and the Exploitation manager will be in charge of collecting information to be shared with EC in order to fill the monitoring questionnaire every two years.

In this document, (the First release of the Exploitation plan) the general plan of the process has been described. In M13 General Assembly, an exploitation workshop will be organized to finalize the KER characterization and starting filling the Business Model Canvas. In the following updates of the Exploitation plan (due at M24, M36 and 48), all the achievement of the described phases will be reported.

6 Exploitation-Identify phase

6.1 Characterization of the AMBIANCE Exploitable results

This section of the document is dedicated to the characterization and deep analysis of the individual and joint exploitable results achieved by the project.

Based on the definition of EU Horizon Europe, the ‘Results’ of the project is any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information, whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected”. The exploitable results can be used by the project partners or by other stakeholders, after their agreement.

It is essential to start with the identification and characterization of the exploitable results. Indeed, not all of what has been achieved throughout course of the project is likely to have an exploitation route. Exploitable results are only those having a potential scientific, economic and social significance. During the project these outcomes provide a mechanism to capture and quantify impact, while, by the end of the project, a way to achieve impact beyond project’s completion.

AMBIANCE follows a systematic approach to the characterization of the Exploitable Results (ER) that provides for reference points and benchmarks.

The first reference point is the category to which the exploitable result belongs and represents a reference point for the identification of the nature of the outcome lays the foundation for a correct exploitation plan. Contrary to common belief, exploitable results do not necessarily correspond to a product or a service, but can be classified as:

- Equipment – the machinery or tools needed to carry out a job; a set of physical tools, devices, kit assembled for a specific purpose.
- Processes – A systematic series of mechanized or chemical operations that are performed in order to produce something.
- Products – something that is made to be sold, usually something that is produced by an industrial process (as a custom but may be personalized upon request).
- Services – offering the above products, processes, equipment, or knowledge as a help to perform a work.
- Knowledge & IP – understanding of or information about a subject that you get by experience or study, either known by one person or by people generally
- Other forms of knowledge – Platform, publications, patent.

The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is a reference tool to assess the technology maturity of the project results.

Figure 53: Technology Readiness Levels

The TRL tools may not apply to all kinds of exploitable results coming from AMBIANCE project. However, it is a helpful instrument for managing the progress of research and development activities since it provides a measure of the current readiness of the exploitable results and a common understanding of their technology status.

Turning innovation actions into concrete value and impact for society is also a matter of thinking ahead. Nevertheless, identifying, shaping and classifying the exploitable results coming from the project do not ensure their use beyond the lifetime of the project. To provide a future to project outcomes, it is of outmost importance to have a clear vision for their exploitation and a customised strategy to follow depending on the nature of the results.

Depending on the TRL reached, there are several routes for carrying out further exploitation, which are presented in the figure below:

Figure 54: Exploitation Visions

The characterization of AMBIANCE outcomes addresses the individual exploitable results obtained by project partners but also the joint and common vision on “AMBIANCE solution”.

Partners outlined a systematic and harmonized characterization of the individual exploitable results describing:

- The results and how it is related with project activities
- The innovation content of the result
- The development status of the innovation

- The category to which the result belongs to
- The ownership of the result
- The expected TRL to be reached
- The exploitation vision and the necessary steps to bring the innovation closer to the market
- The stakeholders to be involved to achieve the exploitation vision
- The intellectual property behind the developed innovation

The first iteration of characterization started at M11 of the project (April 2023), when the Key Exploitable Results characterization table have been shared with the partners. The scheme that the partners followed in collecting information about ERs characterization, is the one shown in Table 1:

Exploitable Results Characterization		
ER Name		
ER Owner		
Other partners involved		
WP involved		
Description		
ER category - Products - Processes - Services - Equipment - Software - Knowledge - IP The list is not exhaustive		
ER Innovation Content		
Keywords related to KER and potential sectors/markets for application		
Exploitation vision	On Going	Planned
Further internal research		
Internal service creation		
Internal product development		
Technology transfer		
Market study		
Prototyping in real world environment		
Complying with existing standards		
Business plan The list is not exhaustive, try to make some hypothesis		
Main markets/users Market segment, potential customers		
Secondary markets/users Not mandatory		

Unit Price and price mechanisms (pay upfront, annual fee...) If not already defined, please include “not available yet”	
Time to market If not already defined, please include “not available yet”	
IP Management	
Background IP <i>Describe the knowledge and or IP regarding this result prior to the project (e.g.: cite patent application no. Wherein relevant, products, conference papers, etc.)</i>	
Type of background IP <i>Select among the following (more than one may apply): Patent (PAT), Utility Model (UM), Trademark (TM), Industrial Design (ID), Plant Variety Rights (PVR), Semiconductor Topography Right (STR), Geographical Indication (GI), Copyright (C), Know-how (KH), Trade Secret (TS), Confidential Information (CI), Database (DB), Prototype (PT), Other</i>	
TRL of Background IP (if applicable) <i>Rate on a TRL1-TRL9 scale</i>	
Exceptions on access to own Background IP to other AMBIANCE project partners <i>Please specify just in case there are admissible exceptions for not (partially) giving access to background IP to one or more partners within the consortium (Art. 31.2)</i>	
Foreground IP <i>Describe the knowledge and or IP regarding this result generated during the project</i>	
TRL of Foreground IP (if applicable) <i>Rate on a TRL1-TRL9 scale</i>	
Exceptions on access to own Background & Foreground IP to other AMBIANCE project partners. According to Consortium Agreement (Art. 31.3) other partners may access IP of the project under fair and reasonable conditions. Please specify just in case there are admissible exceptions for this clause not to (partially) take place.	

Which exploitable claims do you have? **	M =Making the results U = Using the result L = Licensing the result O = Other exploitation means
<p>** The MULO analysis is used to determine the involvement of project partners in each of the Exploitable Results (ER). Partners indicate their intentions corresponding to each of the ERs through writing letters M, U, L and O.</p> <p>The letters stand for:</p> <p>M =Making the results: Making the products, manufacturing and selling or directly implementing it through own facilities and skills.</p> <p>U = Using the result: Using the result, implemented with own knowledge to develop new ranges of products or newer processing. Furthermore, the direct or indirect utilization of foreground in further research activities other than those covered by the project, or for developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or for creating and providing a service.</p> <p>L = Licensing the result: Earning from a negotiation towards third parties outside the consortium.</p> <p>O = Others</p> <p>This is a preliminary MULO analysis. If not already defined, please include “not available yet”</p>	

Table 5: Template for the ERs Characterization

The preliminary information has been collected for some ERs and reported in Annex 1

I IPR strategy

The AMBIANCE project shows the collaboration between universities, research centres, technology providers and industrial companies.

Therefore, an IPR strategy should account for the different needs of each of these internal stakeholders with respect to their exploitation routes.

According to the “*Exploitable results characterization survey*”, shown in the previous chapters, two main groups can be identified:

- those that will disseminate project results mainly in scientific journals, or via active participation in international scientific conferences, workshops as well as other events where the external and connected stakeholders can be addressed directly. In this first group academia and research centres like, e.g., AIMEN, ITAINNOVA, RISE and SUPSI are mainly considered;
- those whose exploitation route will bring new products or services to the reference market or who will use the results of the project to increase the efficiency of their internal production processes. In this group the technology providers and the industry partners are basically considered, which are actively involved in the demonstration and validation scenarios.

While during the project exploitation roadmap will be define, the exploitation activities will be carried out after the end of the project, or in the final months of the DoA. Nevertheless, since the beginning the consortium members have been made aware of the general conditions of all HEU rules for intellectual property rights, with the aim of balancing the need of publicly advertising the knowledge generate in AMBIANCE with the need of the industrial partners to preserve the confidentiality of any data, documents or other material that have actual or potential competitive value.

Therefore, the following directions are considered within this IPR strategy:

- **Safeguarding confidentiality.** As already remarked, during the project and for an appropriate period following the end of the project, still to be agreed by the consortium members, the partners will preserve the confidentiality of any data, documents or other material that have actual or potential value. However, the group acknowledge that the ability to publish results of scientific interest is of great importance. Thus, publication will not be delayed unnecessarily; however, the partners will inform each other in advance of any planned publication in order to allow for any specific protection actions

to be completed. Inclusion of confidential information, especially process data, belonging to other consortium partners will require prior written consent.

Moreover, to guarantee the confidentiality and at the same time to avoid accidental disclosure of information, since the beginning of the project the consortium is using a central Microsoft Teams repository, hosted by ITAINNOVA, with restricted access to the active participants of the project.

- **Protecting Intellectual Property on innovations.** The activities of the AMBIANCE project could lead to new IP and as a result to the filing of patent applications. After the second round of the “*Exploitable results characterization survey*” partners haven’t indicated new patents as the preferred way to protect the new IP generated during the project. However, if this need emerges, the Innovation manager will help partners in the preparation of all the applications for the patenting and/or registration of project results and brands.

Patent applications for AMBIANCE results will be deposited and secured according to the regulations set out in the *European Patent Convention* (EPC) and in concordance with the stipulations in the consortium agreement. For promising markets outside Europe, like e.g., the US, patent applications will also be made to fully exploit the huge market potential.

In case of jointly generated knowledge, the parties that generated such knowledge jointly own it and are encouraged to conclude a *Joint Ownership Agreement* (JOA). In the JOA the joint owners can settle their shares in the results, the modalities for protection by intellectual property rights (IPR) including their responsibilities for filing, maintaining, and defending IPR, and responsibilities and activities in case of infringement of third party IPR, as well as their shares in the related costs. The Innovation Manager will assist the partners in all the documents preparation.

- **Licensing for use.** One of the considerations of *Responsible Partnering* is to ensure maximum beneficial use of knowledge that has been generated partly through public funding. This will be achieved by establishing nonexclusive licenses to several licensees or by granting exclusive licenses to the partner on those uses that he is committed to develop diligently.

7 Conclusion

The document has outlined the strategy to be followed by the consortium with regards to the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. The aim of the plan is to lay the foundation to maximize the impact of the project during its duration and beyond its lifetime. This first draft of the deliverable has been focused on the description of the steps to reach the stated goals and it includes the activities carried out so far and a preliminary description of the exploitable results. Communication activities have been very intense and many communication tools have been deployed to raise awareness of project AMBIANCE. The next actions will be focused on monitoring the progresses of the results and to update the description of their features. Once the results and the partners involved will be more precisely defined, IP right will be managed and issues will be addressed. Market analysis activities will also start to understand which market AMBIANCE results will have to face and a market report will be used as reference point.

Annex I. Exploitable Results Characterization Survey

Here, the collected Exploitable results characterization is reported:

KER#2A Advanced manufacturing processes: Artificial Turf

Characterization of Exploitable results	
ER Name	Advanced manufacturing processes: Artificial Turf
ER Owner	
Other partners involved	
WP involved	WP2
Result/Outcome description Description	
ER category (equipment, process, product, service, knowledge and IP, other)	
ER Innovation Content	
Keywords related to KER and potential sectors/markets for application	
Exploitation vision	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Main markets/users	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Secondary markets/users	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Unit Price and price mechanisms (pay upfront, annual fee...)	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Time to market	To be completed on a subsequent phase
IP Management	
Background IP <i>Describe the knowledge and or IP regarding this result prior to the project (e.g.: cite patent application no. Wherein relevant, products, conference papers, etc.)</i>	Patents: [EN] FIBER FOR ARTIFICIAL TURF ES2437129 T3, [EN] STRATIFIED OBTAINED FROM ARTIFICIAL CESPED SHEETS AND MANUFACTURING PROCEDURE THEREOF (MACHINE-TRANSLATION BY GOOGLE TRANSLATE, NOT LEGALLY BINDING) ES2381945 AA, [EN] METHOD FOR PRODUCING AN ARTIFICIAL FIBER, ARTIFICIAL FIBER PRODUCED AND USE THEREOF ES2462870 AA, [EN] ARTIFICIAL GRASS TURF FOR PADEL COURTS AND INSTALLATION METHOD WO22053721 A1.
Type of background IP <i>Select among the following (more than one may apply): Patent (PAT), Utility Model (UM), Trademark (TM), Industrial Design (ID), Plant Variety Rights (PVR), Semiconductor Topography Right (STR), Geographical Indication (GI), Copyright (C), Know-how (KH), Trade Secret (TS), Confidential Information (CI), Database (DB), Prototype (PT), Other</i>	PAT, CI, PT
TRL of Background IP (if applicable) <i>Rate on a TRL1-TRL9 scale</i>	TR7

Exceptions on access to own Background IP to other AMBIANCE project partners <i>Please specify just in case there are admissible exceptions for not (partially) giving access to background IP to one or more partners within the consortium (Art. 31.2)</i>	
Foreground IP <i>Describe the knowledge and or IP regarding this result generated during the project</i>	
TRL of Foreground IP (if applicable) <i>Rate on a TRL1-TRL9 scale</i>	
Exceptions on access to own Background & Foreground IP to other AMBIANCE project partners. According to Consortium Agreement (Art. 31.3) other partners may access IP of the project under fair and reasonable conditions. Please specify just in case there are admissible exceptions for this clause not to (partially) take place.	
Make	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Use	To be completed on a subsequent phase
License	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Other	To be completed on a subsequent phase

OER#IA Bio-based material Knowledge: bio-based polymers

Characterization of Exploitable results	
ER Name	Bio-based material Knowledge: bio-based polymers
ER Owner	MONDO, ITAINNOVA
Other partners involved	
WP involved	WP2
Result/Outcome description Description	
ER category (equipment, process, product, service, knowledge and IP, other)	Knowledge and IP
ER Innovation Content	
Keywords related to KER and potential sectors/markets for application	
Exploitation vision	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Main markets/users	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Secondary markets/users	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Unit Price and price mechanisms (pay upfront, annual fee...)	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Time to market	To be completed on a subsequent phase
IP Management	
Background IP <i>Describe the knowledge and or IP regarding this result prior to the project (e.g.: cite patent application no. Wherein relevant, products, conference papers, etc.)</i>	Patents: [EN] FIBER FOR ARTIFICIAL TURF ES2437129 T3, [EN] STRATIFIED OBTAINED FROM ARTIFICIAL CESPED SHEETS AND MANUFACTURING PROCEDURE THEREOF (MACHINE-TRANSLATION BY GOOGLE TRANSLATE, NOT LEGALLY BINDING) ES2381945 AA, [EN] METHOD FOR PRODUCING AN ARTIFICIAL FIBER, ARTIFICIAL FIBER PRODUCED AND USE THEREOF ES2462870 AA, [EN] ARTIFICIAL GRASS TURF FOR PADEL COURTS AND INSTALLATION METHOD WO22053721 A1.
Type of background IP <i>Select among the following (more than one may apply): Patent (PAT), Utility Model (UM), Trademark (TM), Industrial Design (ID), Plant Variety Rights (PVR), Semiconductor Topography Right (STR), Geographical Indication (GI), Copyright (C), Know-how (KH), Trade Secret (TS), Confidential Information (CI), Database (DB), Prototype (PT), Other</i>	PAT, CI, PT
TRL of Background IP (if applicable) <i>Rate on a TRL1-TRL9 scale</i>	TRL5

Exceptions on access to own Background IP to other AMBIANCE project partners <i>Please specify just in case there are admissible exceptions for not (partially) giving access to background IP to one or more partners within the consortium (Art. 31.2)</i>	
Foreground IP <i>Describe the knowledge and or IP regarding this result generated during the project</i>	
TRL of Foreground IP (if applicable) <i>Rate on a TRL1-TRL9 scale</i>	
Exceptions on access to own Background & Foreground IP to other AMBIANCE project partners. According to Consortium Agreement (Art. 31.3) other partners may access IP of the project under fair and reasonable conditions. Please specify just in case there are admissible exceptions for this clause not to (partially) take place.	
Make	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Use	To be completed on a subsequent phase
License	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Other	To be completed on a subsequent phase

OER#4 Simulation tools

Characterization of Exploitable results	
ER Name	Simulation tools
ER Owner	ITAINNOVA
Other partners involved	TBD
WP involved	WP2 and WP3
Result/Outcome description Description	Development of physical-data driven models for data handling and pre-processing for each use-case. All accumulated data will be utilised for the development of data-driven models to approximate the optimal set of parameters and settings.
ER category (equipment, process, product, service, knowledge and IP, other)	Service/Simulation executable
ER Innovation Content	Development of multiphysics simulation models for production of artificial turf and 3D-print of furniture. Computational tools for the optimization of the production processes of artificial turf, 3D-print of furniture and panels/bricks construction, based on process-specific Reduced Order Models (ROMs) and Physical-based Digital Twins.
Keywords related to KER and potential sectors/markets for application	Keywords: Physical-based Digital Twins, ROMs, multiphysic, process' parameters optimization
Exploitation vision	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Main markets/users	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Secondary markets/users	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Unit Price and price mechanisms (pay upfront, annual fee...)	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Time to market	Simulation tools
IP Management	
Background IP <i>Describe the knowledge and or IP regarding this result prior to the project (e.g.: cite patent application no. Wherein relevant, products, conference papers, etc.)</i>	Twinkle, an open source application (under GNU GPL license v3) to perform Canonical Polyadic Decomposition (CPD) of tensors. Caelia, commercial application (under GNU GPL license v3) to easily optimize a manufacturing process. STREAM-0D (H2020 -723082) or DIGITbrain (H2020-7952071)
Type of background IP <i>Select among the following (more than one may apply): Patent (PAT), Utility Model (UM), Trademark (TM), Industrial Design (ID), Plant Variety Rights (PVR), Semiconductor Topography Right (STR), Geographical Indication (GI), Copyright (C), Know-how (KH), Trade Secret (TS), Confidential Information (CI), Database (DB), Prototype (PT), Other</i>	DB, C, CO
TRL of Background IP (if applicable) <i>Rate on a TRL1-TRL9 scale</i>	TRL4

Exceptions on access to own Background IP to other AMBIANCE project partners <i>Please specify just in case there are admissible exceptions for not (partially) giving access to background IP to one or more partners within the consortium (Art. 31.2)</i>	
Foreground IP <i>Describe the knowledge and or IP regarding this result generated during the project</i>	It is expected to be able to apply ITAINNOVA's knowledge in the development of ROMs that allow the simulation of complex multiphysics phenomena such as the extrusion of material for manufacturing artificial turf or 3D-printed furniture.
TRL of Foreground IP (if applicable) <i>Rate on a TRL1-TRL9 scale</i>	TRL7
Exceptions on access to own Background & Foreground IP to other AMBIANCE project partners. According to Consortium Agreement (Art. 31.3) other partners may access IP of the project under fair and reasonable conditions. Please specify just in case there are admissible exceptions for this clause not to (partially) take place.	
Make	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Use	To be completed on a subsequent phase
License	To be completed on a subsequent phase
Other	To be completed on a subsequent phase